

Title: “The Intersection of Language, Culture, Technology and Translation in NEP 2020”

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Bio note: Dr Apoorva Poonia is a distinguished alumna of Miranda House, University of Delhi, deeply interested in social and cultural discourse. She has authored a well-received book entitled *Food, Literature and Identity*, demonstrating her expertise in liberal arts and culture studies. She is a recipient of the Junior Research Fellowship from the Ministry of Education, Government of India, and the King’s India Scholarship from Kings College, London. She has numerous publications at national and international conferences. Currently, Dr. Apoorva serves as an Assistant Professor of English. In this role, she has nurtured critical thinking among her students and has made significant contributions to the field of humanities through her research, teaching, and publications.

Abstract:

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 represents a transformative vision for Indian education, aiming to integrate tradition with modernity. This paper examines the intricate interplay of language, culture, technology, and translation within the framework of India's National Education Policy 2020. Using an interdisciplinary approach, it explores how the NEP 2020 incorporates these key components to shape educational practices and outcomes. First, the chapter examines the linguistic aspect of the NEP 2020, specifically focusing on its promotion of multilingualism and learning in mother tongues in addition to multilingual competency. Second, it scrutinises the cultural elements woven throughout NEP 2020, examining how the curriculum integrates various cultural content to help students develop a sense of inclusivity and identity. Third, it examines how technology aligns with the NEP 2020, assessing its potential to create innovative, accessible, and customised learning experiences. Finally, it examines the importance of translation in implementing the NEP 2020 by exploring how it facilitates communication and information sharing across language barriers. Through an analysis of these interrelated elements, this research-based paper

provides an understanding of the all-encompassing methodology of the NEP 2020 and its capacity to revolutionise the Indian educational landscape.

Keywords: National Education Policy 2020, Language, Culture, Technology, Translation, NEP 2020, Developed India 2047

Introduction:

The National Education Policy 2020 is a massive shift in the Indian education system. For the first time, India has witnessed an education policy that considers the development of India, its cultural traditions, and the prosperity of its people as the primary goals of education. It characterises the present period and focuses on the years to come in the 21st century. Its goal is to make it more responsive to the demands of the 21st century. This policy has been formulated to provide equal and inclusive education, emphasising holistic development, flexibility, promotion of research and innovation, and multidisciplinary learning. It achieves this by encouraging the use of the mother tongue and local language as a medium of instruction, particularly at the foundational and preparatory stages, to preserve cultural identity and foster mutual understanding. It also highlights the connection between technical and vocational training and digital literacy at every level. It also emphasises the need for translation to promote knowledge sharing across communities.

It attempts to incorporate language, culture, technology, and translation in a manner that provides freedom from the conflict between modernity and antiquity, which has been an inevitable consequence of Indian education since independence. It is structured so that it aims to create a more flexible, inclusive and holistic education system that prepares students for lifelong learning while contributing to the country's socioeconomic development. An evolved system of education is key to a nation's development. The National Education Policy 2020 is unique in that it aims to provide education that will enhance India's overall development. Thus, the National Education Policy 2020 is a positive step towards realising the dream of a 'Developed India' by 2047.

Promotion of Multilingualism:

“The French speak French, the Germans speak German, the Americans speak English- but Indians speak Punjabi, or Gujarati or Malayalam, and it does not make us any less Indian.”

- Dr Shashi Tharoor, *The Times of India*.

Celebrating India’s linguistic diversity, author Shashi Tharoor highlights the language pluralism in India in his article on Independence Day. He argues that linguistically, we are all minorities in India, and a look at our currency notes, with their denominations, spelt out in 18 languages and nearly as many scripts, makes the point. On the linguistic diversity of India, he further says:

The constitution of India recognises 23 languages today, and in fact, there are 35 Indian languages that are each spoken by more than a million people- and these are languages with their scripts, grammatical structures and cultural assumptions, not just dialects (and if we count dialects, there are more than 22,000)(toi.com)

As Dr. Tharoor points out, pluralism is inherent in the very nature of this country. It’s a choice inevitably made by the country’s geography, reaffirmed by its history and reflected in its ethnography. Hence, as long as we can assert our dedication towards our country, the use of any and every language is justified. And it is this multitude of languages that NEP 2020 attempts to celebrate.

The importance of language in the policy can be understood because the word ‘language’ has appeared 206 times in its 66-page document. Instead of discussing any particular language and culture, the document emphasises diversity, focusing on all Indian languages. It attempts to consider Indian languages holistically at the national level. Schools will now offer options for students to learn Indian languages such as Tamil, Telugu, Odia, Pali, Prakrat, etc. It gives particular importance to the mother tongue and local and regional languages. About the use of the mother tongue in education, it says, “NEP 2020 makes the mother tongue the medium of instruction until Grade 5. The policy ensures that quality

textbooks, including science, are available in local languages. Any gaps between the child's language and the medium they are taught will be bridged.” (education.gov.in)

It maintains the policy of a three-language formula, which also provides the opportunity to study foreign languages, such as Korean, Spanish, Thai, and Russian, as optional languages in secondary education. This will further develop the student’s understanding of global cultures and knowledge systems. It is noteworthy that it puts all languages on an equal pedestal.

For the first time in India's history, inputs were gathered from approximately 2.5 lakh gram panchayats, 6,600 blocks, and 650 districts to formulate an education policy. Suggestions were gathered and brainstormed by academicians, teachers, parents, public representatives, and students. Thus, the National Education Policy 2020 was designed in response to public aspirations, national needs, and challenges. One of the concerns it raises is the preservation of local Indian languages. It is reported that due to inadequate and improper attention to Indian languages, more than 220 languages have become extinct over the last 50 years. According to the UNESCO list, 197 more Indian languages are mentioned as endangered. This threat of extinction is more significant for the languages of small and scriptless linguistic communities.

A language is the reflection of one’s society. Language directly connects with that region's culture, environment, food, lifestyle and identity. When a language disappears, a culture, a history, a civilisation ends. With the destruction of a dialect, the precious traditional knowledge it contains, including its folk songs, folk tales, vocabulary, and expressions, as well as the wisdom accumulated over thousands of years, is also lost in the depths of time. Thus, there was a need for an ideological initiative to promote language conservation. Indian languages will not be able to secure their rightful place unless they are used as languages of knowledge and science. The way such language questions have been addressed afresh in the National Education Policy raises considerable hopes. It resolves the issue of language preservation by making education accessible in these languages. On this matter, Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi said, "This is a much-awaited reform in the field of education, which will change the lives of millions of people. Under the 'Ek Bharat-Shreshtha Bharat' initiative, Indian languages, including Sanskrit, will be promoted.” (pmonradio.nic)

Integration of cultural elements:

“Language is the road map of a culture. It tells you where its people come from and where they are going”.

-Rita Mae Brown (goodreads.com)

Language is an integral part of the culture of any country. It is the medium of expression of every civilised nation. It is the carrier of its culture. It is not just a system of sounds, letters, and vocabulary; it also brings many ideas. It provides a perspective on the world. These perspectives are best represented through literature, which is why literature is referred to as ‘the mirror of society’. However, these perspectives and narratives are genuine when people document them in their regional language.

According to the famous sociologist Mac Iver, culture is evident in our daily behaviour, as seen in language, literature, art, religion, entertainment, and pleasure. It is the expression of our nature in the ways of living and thinking (1). Thus, there is a profound and integral relationship between language and culture. Without language, the promotion of culture is not possible. In his ‘Mann Ki Baat’ programme, Prime Minister Narendra Modi frequently emphasises the importance of using one’s native language to promote one’s cultural identity. He says:

Just as our mother shapes our lives, our mother tongue also shapes our lives. Even after 75 years of independence, some people are living in such mental conflict, due to which they feel hesitant about their language, their clothes, and their food habits. However, this is not the case anywhere else in the world. It is our mother tongue; we should speak it with pride, and our India is so rich in languages that it cannot be compared. (pmonradio.nic)

The National Education Policy 2020 is mindfully designed with India’s ‘unity in diversity’ in mind. It emphasises the promotion, restoration, and propagation of Indian traditions, culture, and languages. It attempts to do so by fostering teaching in native languages, promoting cultural exchange programmes and integrating traditional knowledge systems and indigenous practices. India is home to the wisdom of ‘Vasudev Kutumbkam’ and art like ‘yoga’. Due to India’s immense knowledge base, Nobel laureate Rabindranath Tagore has likened India to a

'great human ocean'. It is safe to say that its indigenous knowledge base is no less than that of any other country. Thus, NEP-2020 commits to nurturing a culturally vibrant and inclusive education system that fosters a deep appreciation for India's cultural diversity, heritage, and values among future generations. By incorporating these cultural elements into the education system, it seeks to promote national unity while promoting global citizenship.

The role of technology:

Education is a social responsibility in all the advanced countries of the world. Despite the spread of a global tragedy such as the Coronavirus, the propagation of education did not stop. Such a tragedy has taught the world the importance of technology in education. The key role outlined for technology in NEP 2020 is to facilitate universal access to quality education through digital platforms. Utilising technology, the policy aims to reach learners in remote areas, ensuring that no student is left behind. Despite economic disparities and geographical challenges, all students in India should have the opportunity to study and reach their full potential, as outlined in the National Education Policy 2020, in a sensitive and thoughtful manner.

The Covid period has made the entire society understand the power of information technology. During this period, it was verified that information technology can conveniently deliver education to everyone. Despite various efforts spanning 70 years, education has been unable to establish its reach in the country's remote areas. However, with the aid of technology, the spread of education to every student has become possible through online teaching. However, the NEP 2020 does not consider teaching through technology as an alternative to general education; instead, it is merely a supportive mode of education. The primary purpose of this supportive mode of education is to ensure continuity of learning.

There is a bidirectional relationship between technology and education at all levels. Given the rapid rate of technological development and the sheer creativity of teachers and entrepreneurs who understand and utilise technology, it is clear that technology will undoubtedly impact education in numerous ways. New technology areas, such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, blockchain, smartboards, handheld computing devices, adaptive computing, and other types of software, will change not only what students learn but also how they learn.

To make learning quick and easy, NEP 2020 has adopted technology-based learning. It promotes the use of learning apps for languages, online resources, multimedia materials, and other digital tools, in conjunction with traditional teaching approaches, to encourage active participation in second language acquisition. The emphasis under NEP 2020 is on developing and disseminating digital content in regional languages, thereby enhancing accessibility to quality education for children from diverse linguistic backgrounds. The policy aims to bridge the language barrier by utilising technology to create educational materials in various languages, thereby ensuring that all learners can benefit from digital resources regardless of their linguistic abilities. Technological advancements also provide opportunities for students from diverse linguistic backgrounds to communicate with speakers of other languages, promoting multiculturalism.

NEP 2020 encourages educators to integrate cultural content into EdTech platforms and digital resources. By incorporating elements of India's rich cultural heritage into online learning materials, this policy fosters cultural awareness, appreciation, and inclusiveness among students. It helps learners develop a comprehensive understanding of their own culture, as well as that of others. Thus, NEP 2020 in India combines language, culture, and technology by promoting multilingualism, using technology for language learning, delivering digital content in regional languages and integrating cultural perspectives into educational technology. When these aspects are interwoven, this policy aims to establish an inclusive, culturally enriched learning environment that leverages technological potential to empower students, while celebrating diversity related to language and culture within the Indian context.

The Importance of Translation:

So far, in the Indian educational landscape, regional languages have never been taken seriously. The NEP 2020 focuses majorly on teaching in regional languages. This raises concerns about the shortage of regional language teachers with higher qualifications and highlights the need to develop a large cadre of such teachers. From a linguistic perspective, the key is to integrate Indian language teaching programs at every level, from elementary school to higher education, and develop a mechanism for creating high-quality, diverse content in regional languages, continuously updating it according to the resources available in

mainstream languages. This is only feasible through translation. Thus, translation is central to the National Education Policy 2020.

Through translation, updated material for teaching and learning should be created, the criteria for translation should be established, the quality of the translated text should be assessed, and books, manuscripts, records, neglected rare texts, and unique creations reflecting timeless Indian culture should be exchanged in Indian languages. There should be translations, even in foreign languages, and ideal translations of mythology, so that the actual image of Indian wisdom and talent emerges before the world. Provisions have also been made that dictionaries of Indian languages should become encyclopedias, e-thesauruses should be created, updated glossaries should be created, and the vast vocabulary of Indian languages should be made rich and complete. The path has also been paved for translating a service-providing discipline. This will enable the dissemination and exchange of knowledge and wealth available in Indian and foreign languages. The most important thing is that adequate material should be translated from world languages to further enrich Indian languages, as English, French, German, Hebrew, Korean, and Japanese have already done.

Therefore, at the higher education level and other knowledge disciplines, two more things from the linguistic point of view have been emphasised, albeit belatedly. One is that strong departments and programs in Indian languages and comparative literature will start nationwide. Secondly, departments with high-quality and skill-based translation and interpretation programs will be established in the country's universities. To meet the expectations of a multilingual nation and provide access to high-quality knowledge materials and other written or spoken content available in Indian and foreign languages, it was announced that the Indian Institute of Translation and Interpretation (IITI) would be established. Accepting translation as an independent discipline and an essential need of the nation is undoubtedly a far-sighted decision.

Conclusion:

The New Education Policy 2020 is a practical and helpful policy from many perspectives. It contributes to the 'Indianization' of education by strengthening and promoting Indian languages. It also keeps pace with modern developments in various fields

of knowledge, such as science, information technology, and digitalisation, thus making it a brilliant amalgamation of culture and technology. Translation is at the core of this structure, which will help establish India as a vibrant knowledge-based society and make it a global knowledge superpower. Thus, this excellent coordination of language, culture, technology and translation in the National Education Policy 2020 will revolutionise the Indian educational landscape. It will prove to be a milestone in building a Developed India by 2047.

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